

Kinetics of iodine complexes with Triton X-100 in aqueous and non-aqueous media

Papia Ganguly^{a*} and Benoy B. Bhowmik^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Maulana Azad College, Kolkata-700 013, India

E-mail : pganguly@eth.net Fax : 91-033-24965065

^bCentre for Surface Science, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

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Abstract : Triton X-100 (TX-100) forms 1 : 1 charge-transfer (CT) complexes with iodine in aqueous as well as in carbon tetrachloride solution. The equilibrium constant (K_c) and molar extinction coefficient (ϵ_c) of iodine-TX-100 complex in both media have been determined from the spectral studies. From the kinetic studies of complex formation in both media, the rate constants (both forward and backward) and equilibrium constant have also been determined. The same equilibrium constant and rate constant values indicate that the hydrophilic head group of TX-100 is involved in the complex formation with iodine in both media.

Keywords : Kinetics, iodine complexes, Triton X-100.

In one of our earlier report¹ of CT interaction between I_2 and TX-100, we concluded that in aqueous medium, oxygen atom of the oxyethylene (hydrophilic) group donates one of the lone pair of electrons to iodine whereas in carbon tetrachloride solution, the substituted benzene ring donates π -electron to iodine for CT interaction. To verify this, reinvestigation of spectral studies of CT interaction of I_2 with TX-100 in both media has been made to evaluate the equilibrium constant (K_c) and molar extinction coefficient (ϵ_c) of I_2 -TX-100 complex along with kinetic studies of the complex formation for determining the rate constants (both forward and backward) and equilibrium constant. The results are presented here.

Results and discussion

The visible absorption spectra of mixed solutions with a fixed concentration of iodine (2.7×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) and varying concentrations of TX-100 above cmc (1×10^{-2} - 5×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³), the cmc being 2.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, in aqueous medium at 298 K are shown in Fig. 1a. The absorption spectra of I_2 in water show the absorption maximum at 460 nm. A remarkable change is observed in the spectra of the mixed solution of I_2 and TX-100 in aqueous medium, where the absorption maximum has shifted from 460 nm to 441 nm with an isosbestic point at 496 nm which indicates 1 : 1 complex formation. Similarly, the visible absorption spectra of mixed solu-

tions with a fixed concentration of iodine (5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) and varying concentrations of TX-100 above the critical reverse micelle concentration (the critical reverse micelle concentration being 0.89×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) of TX-100 (1×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ to 5×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³) in carbon tetrachloride at 298 K are shown in Fig. 1b. The absorption spectra of iodine in carbon tetrachloride show the absorption maximum at 516 nm. In presence of TX-100 the absorption maximum of I_2 has been shifted to 430 nm with an isosbestic point at 473 nm indicating 1 : 1 complex formation between I_2 and TX-100 in reverse micelle. The spectral data were employed to calculate the equilibrium constant and molar extinction coefficient of TX-100 interaction with I_2 in aqueous and carbon tetrachloride media. For 1 : 1 complex, these values can be determined by using Scott equation² in the following modified form :

$$[I_2] [TX-100] / l(d - d_0) = [TX-100] / \epsilon_c - \epsilon_0 + 1/K_c (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0) \quad (1)$$

where $[I_2]$ and $[TX-100]$ are the initial concentrations of I_2 and TX-100, respectively, l is the optical pathlength of the solution; d and d_0 are the absorbances of iodine at the absorption maximum of the complex with and without TX-100, respectively, and ϵ_c and ϵ_0 are the respective molar extinction coefficients of the complex and iodine at the absorption maximum of the complex. The values of

Fig. 1. (a) Visible absorption spectra of mixed solutions with concentration of I_2 ($[I_2] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and varying concentrations of TX-100 ($[TX-100] \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$): (1) 0, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 3.0, (5) 4.0 and (6) 5.0 in aqueous solution at 298 K. (b) Visible absorption spectra of mixed solution with a fixed concentration of I_2 ($[I_2] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and varying concentrations of TX-100 ($[TX-100] \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$): (1) 0, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 3.0, (5) 4.0 and (6) 5.0 in carbon tetrachloride at 298 K.

K_c and ϵ_c were calculated from eq. (1) by plotting $[I_2][TX-100]/d - d_0$ versus $[TX-100]$. The plots were found to be linear in both cases confirming 1 : 1 complex formation in aqueous and carbon tetrachloride media. This is the shifted I_2 absorption band in both media, the exact CT transition occurs below 300 nm where TX-100 absorbs predominantly.

Kinetic study of the complex formation has been made considering the following reversible reaction between I_2 and $TX-100^3$,

and the corresponding rate equation is

$$-d[I_2]/dt = -d[TX-100]/dt = d[I_2-TX-100]/dt = \frac{k_1[I_2][TX-100] - k_{-1}[I_2-TX-100]}{k_1[I_2][TX-100] - k_{-1}[I_2-TX-100]} \quad (3)$$

if the concentrations of I_2 , TX-100 and its complex at

zero time are represented by a , b and c and those at time t by $(a - x)$, $(b - x)$ and $(c + x)$ respectively, eq. (3) becomes

$$dx/dt = k_1(a - x)(b - x) - k_{-1}(c + x) \quad (4)$$

At equilibrium the net rate is zero and

$$k_1(a - x_e)(b - x_e) = k_{-1}(c + x_e) \quad (5)$$

The value of x in the equilibrium state is x_e , a constant independent of time in a given experiment, when $[TX-100] \gg [I_2]$ i.e. $a \gg b$ which implies $a \gg x_e$ and x , eqs. (4) and (6) become

$$dx/dt = k_1a(b - x) - k_{-1}(c + x) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } k_1a(b - x_e) = k_{-1}(c + x_e) \quad (7)$$

Solving for c , we obtain

$$c = k_1a(b - x_e)/k_{-1} - x_e$$

Substituting this expression in eq. (6) yields

$$dx/dt = (k_1a + k_{-1})(x_e - x) = \ln(x_e - x_0) / (x_e - x)$$

Integrating from $x = x_0$ at $t = 0$ to x at t

$$(k_1a + k_{-1})t = \ln(x_e - x_0) / (x_e - x) \quad (8)$$

This rate equation is formally quite similar to the pseudo first order equation³, except that the measured rate constant is now the sum of the forward and backward rate constants. Since absorbance (d) of the complex at the intense CT absorption band or shifted complex absorption band is linear in x , the change in x can be replaced by the change in this property

$$(k_1a + k_{-1})t = \ln(d_e - d_0) / (d_e - d_t) \quad (9)$$

where d_0 , d_t and d_e are the values of absorbance of the complex at intense CT band or shifted complex band at time zero, t and infinite time (or equilibrium state), respectively. The plot of $\ln(d_e - d_0) / (d_e - d_t)$ versus time, t gives the slope which is equal to $(k_1a + k_{-1})$ i.e. $k_1[\text{TX-100}] + k_{-1}$. When the values of $k_1[\text{TX-100}] + k_{-1}$ are plotted against $[\text{TX-100}]$, the slope will give the value of k_1 while the intercept will give the value of k_{-1} .

From these plots, all the parameters of kinetic studies such as rate constants for the forward and backward reactions and equilibrium constants from these rate constants have been calculated. The values in aqueous and carbon tetrachloride solutions are : K_c ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1}$) 95.23; 114.30; e_c ($\text{m}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) 433.0, 299.50; k_1 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) 3.703, 5.26; k_{-1} (s^{-1}) 0.038, 0.047; K_c ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) 97.46, 111.91 respectively. The equilibrium constant values obtained from time independent spectral studies and time depen-

dent absorbance values from kinetic studies are almost same confirming that the two independent methods are correct.

Experimental

A.R. quality iodine (B.D.H.) was used after resublimation. A.R. grade Triton X-100 supplied by Sigma Chemicals and spectrograde carbon tetrachloride supplied by B.D.H. were used as such. Absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 200 spectrophotometer with a matched pair of stoppered fused silica cells of 1 cm optical pathlength. For kinetic study of the complex formation between I_2 and TX-100, one of the 1 cm cells has almost been filled with a definite volume of iodine solution of known concentration and the absorbance was recorded at 440 nm against the corresponding solvent. The time dependence record has been started with the introduction of 0.1 ml concentrated TX-100 to the solution of iodine by a syringe pulling needle into the solution.

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